

DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF CONVENTIONAL PAP SMEAR AND LIQUID-BASED CYTOLOGY FOR CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING

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Abstract

Objective:

To determine the accuracy of conventional Pap smear and liquid-based cytology for cervical cancer screening taking histopathology as gold standard.

Methods:

This cross-sectional study involving 153 suspected patients of cervical cancer was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, DHQ Hospital, DG Khan, from July 2024 to January 2025. All participants underwent a series of diagnostic procedures, including Pap smear, colposcopy, and cervical biopsy. Considering biopsy as the gold standard, the sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, and overall diagnostic accuracy of both Pap smear and LBC were evaluated.

Results:

The mean age was 39.5 years with a standard deviation of 7.5 years. Regarding parity, 15.0% (23 patients) were primiparous, while 85.0% (130 patients) were multiparous. In terms of menstrual status, 70.5% (108 patients) were premenopausal, and 29.5% (45 patients) were menopausal. The diagnostic accuracy of the PAP smear and liquid-based cytology (LBC) was assessed. The sensitivity of the PAP smear was 47.2%, while that of LBC was higher at 66.0%. The specificity was comparable between the two methods, with the PAP smear at 90.0% and LBC at 89.0%. The positive predictive value (PPV) was 71.4% for the PAP smear and 76.1% for LBC. Additionally, the negative predictive value (NPV) was 76.3% for the PAP smear and 83.2% for LBC.

Conclusion:

This comparative study shows that Liquid-Based Cytology (LBC) has significantly higher diagnostic accuracy than Pap smear in cervical cancer screening. These results support the potential use of LBC in routine screening programs, particularly in settings with adequate resources and infrastructure.

INTRODUCTION:

Cervical cancer represents a major public health concern worldwide, ranking as the fourth most common cancer and a leading cause of cancer-related deaths.¹ Early changes in cervical cells, such as intraepithelial lesions, can be detected years before invasive cancer develops. This early

detection capability led to the implementation of screening programs across the globe.² The development of the Pap smear test, pioneered by Dr. George Papanicolaou and colleagues, revolutionized cervical cancer screening by enabling the identification of precancerous changes through cytological examination of cells

scraped from the cervix.³ Consequently, the use of Pap smear testing has considerably reduced the incidence of advanced cervical cancer.⁴

Traditional Pap smears often yielded misleading negative results. Factors such as errors during sample collection, the presence of blood or mucus that hindered accurate reading, along with issues in screening and interpretation, contributed to this problem.⁵ Over the past 15 years, various cytological techniques have been introduced to improve the sensitivity of Pap smears. Among these, liquid-based cytology (LBC) has emerged as the most notable and widely adopted method.⁶ This approach offers several advantages, including the elimination of blood, mucus, and obscuring cells from samples, reducing the number of inadequate or unsatisfactory specimens, decreasing the time required for examination, enabling HPV testing from the same sample, and preserving leftover material for additional tests.⁷

This study has been planned to compare the results of conventional PAP smear and LBC preparation for cervical cancer screening in women presenting in our local setting. The study results would provide local data on the sensitivity and specificity of PAP smears and LBCs, enabling better practice in the future.

METHODS:

This cross-sectional study involving 153 suspected patients of cervical cancer was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, DHQ Hospital, DG Khan, from July 2024 to January 2025. The inclusion criteria were women with one or more clinical symptoms of abnormal vaginal bleeding, pain in the lower abdomen or postcoital bleeding, aged 25 to 64 years, and duration of symptoms \geq 1 month. While exclusion criteria were women with a history of prior treatment for cervical intraepithelial neoplasia or cervical cancer, and women who had undergone total abdominal hysterectomy. Approval from the hospital ethical committee was obtained.

The baseline data collected included age, gravida, para, menstrual status, residential area, presence of diabetes mellitus, smoking habits, and obesity. All participants underwent a series of diagnostic procedures, including Pap smear, colposcopy, and cervical biopsy. The Pap smears were prepared using Ayre's spatula, while

endocervical sampling for liquid-based cytology (LBC) was performed with a Cyto brush to collect exfoliated cells. All sample collection procedures adhered to established standard protocols. Under colposcopic guidance, targeted biopsies were taken, and the tissue specimens were sent for histopathological examination to determine underlying pathology. Samples were obtained with an Ayers spatula for traditional Pap smears and a cervix brush for liquid-based cytology. The collected specimens were prepared and stained following the Papanicolaou technique, and the findings were categorized according to the Bethesda 2001 System.⁸ While histopathology findings were taken as the gold standard for the diagnosis of malignancy.

The analysis was conducted using SPSS version 23. The variables of age and BMI were reported as means with standard deviations. Data related to gravida, para, menstrual status, residence area, presence of diabetes mellitus, smoking habits, obesity, and cytological results from Pap smear, LBC, and biopsy were expressed as frequencies and percentages. Considering biopsy as the gold standard, the sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, and overall diagnostic accuracy of both Pap smear and LBC were evaluated.

RESULTS:

The baseline characteristics of the 153 patients included in the study are as follows: The mean age was 39.5 years with a standard deviation of 7.5 years. Regarding parity, 15.0% (23 patients) were primiparous, while 85.0% (130 patients) were multiparous. In terms of menstrual status, 70.5% (108 patients) were premenopausal, and 29.5% (45 patients) were menopausal. Diabetes was present in 16.3% (25 patients), and 5.2% (8 patients) were smokers. The mean body mass index (BMI) was 28.5 kg/m² with a standard deviation of 3.4. Additionally, 25.4% (39 patients) were classified as obese (Table 1).

The frequency of cytological and histopathological findings among patients was as follows: on PAP smear, 22.9% (35 patients) had malignant lesions, while 77.1% (118 patients) had non-malignant findings. Liquid-based cytology (LBC) identified malignant lesions in 30.0% (46 patients) and non-malignant findings in 70.0% (107 patients). Histopathological examination revealed malignant lesions in

34.6% (53 patients), with the remaining 65.4% (100 patients) showing non-malignant results (Table 2).

The diagnostic accuracy of the PAP smear and liquid-based cytology (LBC) was assessed. The sensitivity of the PAP smear was 47.2%, while that of LBC was higher at 66.0%. The specificity

was comparable between the two methods, with the PAP smear at 90.0% and LBC at 89.0%. The positive predictive value (PPV) was 71.4% for the PAP smear and 76.1% for LBC. Additionally, the negative predictive value (NPV) was 76.3% for the PAP smear and 83.2% for LBC (Table 3).

Table 1. Baseline Patient’s Characteristics (N=153).

Age (Years)	39.5±7.5
Parity (%)	
Primipara	23 (15.0%)
Multipara	130 (85.0%)
Menstrual status (%)	
Premenopausal	108 (70.5%)
Menopausal	45 (29.5%)
Diabetes (%)	25 (16.3%)
Smoking (%)	08 (5.2%)
BMI (Kg/m ²)	28.5±3.4
Obesity (%)	39 (25.4%)

Table 2. Frequency of Cytological / Histopathological findings.

PAP Smear (%)	
Malignant	35 (22.9%)
Non-malignant	118 (77.1%)
LBC (%)	
Malignant	46 (30.0%)
Non-malignant	107 (70.0%)
Histopathology (%)	
Malignant	53 (34.6%)
Non-malignant	100 (65.4%)

Table 3. Diagnostic Accuracies of PAP Smear and LBC.

	PAP Smear	LBC
Sensitivity	47.2%	66.0%
Specificity	90.0%	89.0%
Positive Predictive Value (PPV)	71.4%	76.1%
Negative Predictive Value (NPV)	76.3%	83.2%

DISCUSSION:

LBC is a technique that allows cells to be maintained in a monolayer, thereby enhancing the detection of precancerous lesions by ensuring better specimen adequacy. This method leads to an increased identification of histologically confirmed neoplastic and preneoplastic conditions, ultimately making cervical cancer screening more effective.⁹ Additionally, it helps reduce the overdiagnosis

of benign processes. Despite numerous studies and systematic reviews, debates continue regarding its diagnostic accuracy. MLBC presents a cost-effective alternative suitable for resource-limited settings, offering a more affordable option compared to the traditionally used automated LBC methods.¹⁰ Although LBC incurs a higher upfront testing expense, its advantages—such as a lower rate of inadequate smears, enhanced diagnostic clarity,

and the option for HPV co-testing—render it a cost-effective choice over time, particularly in settings with large testing volumes like public health clinics.¹¹ The results endorse adopting this method within national screening initiatives, especially as Pakistan gradually shifts to HPV-based screening strategies that include cytology.

Shobana R and colleagues conducted a study involving 100 patients. They found that 28% of the cases exhibited cytological abnormalities when using liquid-based cytology (LBC), while the conventional Pap smear detected abnormalities in only 22% of cases. The sensitivity and specificity of the Pap smear for identifying low-grade squamous intraepithelial lesions (LSIL) were 40% and 93%, respectively, and for high-grade lesions (HSIL), they were 50% and 100%. In comparison, LBC showed a sensitivity of 66% and a specificity of 94% for LSIL, whereas for HSIL, both sensitivity and specificity reached 100% and 96%. Overall, the conventional Pap smear demonstrated lower sensitivity and specificity, at 55.5% and 83.7%, respectively, whereas LBC exhibited higher accuracy with sensitivity of 83% and specificity of 86.5%.⁶ In a separate study focused on cervical cancer screening, 97 women participated. The median age was 41 years, with ages ranging from 20 to 70. All participants underwent Liquid Based Cytology (LBC) and Conventional Pap Smear (CPS) testing. However, only 41 women received biopsies for histopathological confirmation. Among these, 18 women were diagnosed with cervical dysplasia or cancer, representing a prevalence of 43.9%. When compared to histopathology as the reference standard, the sensitivity of CPS was 33.33%, with a specificity of 95.65%. LBC demonstrated a sensitivity of 22.22% and a specificity of 95.65%.¹²

This research encountered several limitations. Initially, the relatively small sample size was recruited from a single tertiary care hospital, potentially restricting the applicability of the results to a wider population. Additionally, although the same patients were subjected to both Liquid-Based Cytology (LBC) and Conventional Pap Smear (CPS) sampling, variability in cytological interpretation among observers, despite efforts to blind assessors, might have affected the diagnostic accuracy.

Finally, the study did not include an evaluation of cost-effectiveness, which remains a crucial factor especially in public healthcare systems with limited resources.

Conclusion:

This comparative study shows that Liquid-Based Cytology (LBC) has significantly higher diagnostic accuracy than Pap smear in cervical cancer screening. These results support the potential use of LBC in routine screening programs, particularly in settings with adequate resources and infrastructure.

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